

Tailoring magnetic properties and suppressing anisotropy in permalloy films by deposition in a rotating magnetic field

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Abstract

We investigate the optimal deposition conditions for permalloy ($\text{Ni}_{81}\text{Fe}_{19}$) thin films fabricated via magnetron sputtering to achieve soft magnetic films for magnetoresistive sensing applications. The films are grown with different deposition techniques like sputtering and molecular beam epitaxy and parameters, including varying inert gas pressure and deposition power, and with different magnetic fields applied during the growth. Our approach enables sputtering of permalloy films with low coercivity while keeping high anisotropic magnetoresistance values. We develop a robust method to characterize the intrinsic magnetic anisotropy of the films that is not dominated by local defects and demonstrate the possibility of magnetic anisotropy suppression via implementing a rotating magnetic field during sputtering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Permalloy ($\text{Fe}_{75 \leq x \leq 82}\text{Ni}_{1-x}$, Py) is an archetypical soft magnetic material [1] that possesses highly desirable properties such as an extremely low magnetostriction, a low coercivity and a vanishingly low magnetic anisotropy, making it attractive for a vast range of applications [2–9], which in turn demand easy tailoring of magnetic and electric properties. Thin films of permalloy are in-plane magnetized by their shape anisotropy, but due to non-ideal growth conditions they usually exhibit an additional slight and possibly detrimental uniaxial in-plane anisotropic behavior. The coercivity and anisotropy of permalloy employed in low-field magnetic sensors, magnetic domain-wall logic and memory devices should be as low as possible [10]. Low anisotropy and coercivity of permalloy is highly desirable for anisotropic magnetoresistance (AMR) sensors [11], which are in high interest for detecting and responding to external magnetic fields. AMR sensors are in high demand in areas where high sensitivity and flexibility of design are required, in particular they can be used in wearable electronics for navigation, medical diagnosis and health monitoring [12].

Py films used in industrial magnetoresistive devices are in most cases prepared by magnetron sputtering due to its high deposition rates, stability, flexibility in terms of materials, achievable film thicknesses down to the sub-nm range and the range of controllable pa-

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rameters, such as the plasma power, chamber pressure, sputtering angle and deposition temperature. Permalloy properties to be tailored are the magnetic anisotropy [2, 3, 13, 14], the coercivity [15, 16], the exchange stiffness [17], and the damping constant [18–20]. Among reported approaches are modifying the composition (varying the nickel to iron ratio [14, 21–23] or doping with transition [24], noble [20, 24], and rare-earth [18, 25] metals), material stack variations [26–29] to modify the permalloy texture and avoid magnetically “dead” interfacial layers, optimizing deposition [10, 16, 30, 31] and annealing parameters [13, 17], including field annealing [13], tilting the target [14, 15, 32], applying external fields during deposition [14, 32, 33], and the use of textured substrates [34–36] to promote anisotropy. Even though the material has been widely investigated for several decades, the origins of different sources of anisotropy including magnetocrystalline and growth-condition-induced anisotropies are still a topic of intense discussion. Very early theories describe the crystalline anisotropy of permalloy via a simple vector sum of separate atomic moments [37], while recent studies consider atomic orbital hybridisation in a variable chemical environment [38] and the associated charge redistribution [22]. The properties of permalloy can be significantly modified via field annealing, but the mechanism of the effect is still being discussed. Various mechanisms resulting in uniaxial anisotropy in permalloy were proposed, including Fe-Fe pair ordering effects [39], magnetostrictive contributions [40], and defects including vacancies, contaminants, and grain boundaries [41]. A recent study found that the electrical resistivity of polycrystalline permalloy films is higher along the hard-axis direction than along the easy axis, which is in agreement with proposals that directional order can induce magnetic anisotropy in permalloy [33, 42].

In addition to inducing anisotropy, studies have also investigated ways to suppress it: while permalloy films that are magnetically shielded during deposition still demonstrate a residual anisotropy [43], annealing in a rotating field is reported to fully suppress the anisotropy but it is accompanied by an increase of film coercivity [13, 32]. Rotating the sample during deposition with respect to a tilted target drastically decreases both, the coercivity and the anisotropy, but only down to a certain plateau [33]. Finally, Py deposition at normal incidence in a rotating external field of 3 mT was reported to result in isotropic properties when averaging over the entire film [32], however these films still exhibit anisotropy on a local scale as it can be concluded from the observation of magnetization ripples on a scale of 100 μm .

All the above-mentioned approaches to minimize magnetic anisotropy rely on obtaining polycrystalline samples with a random orientation of crystallites, so that the local anisotropy averages out and the samples do not exhibit a net anisotropy [44, 45]. However, *fcc* metals have a tendency to develop a (111) texture to minimize the surface energy, resulting in an intrinsic compressive stress due to the incorporation of surface atoms in the film caused by the high adatom energy [46]; this is also linked with a higher density and lower roughness and coercivity of the resulting films [15, 31, 47].

To summarize, a range of different factors impact the anisotropy of thin polycrystalline permalloy films and while the anisotropy of permalloy can be reduced, residual sources of anisotropy often remain, which can be detrimental for device performance, calling for further approaches to growth optimization. Furthermore, it is of paramount importance that robust techniques are established that can reliably benchmark the influence of varied deposition conditions on the film quality. Since extended thin films frequently contain macroscopic defects that occur randomly and are not necessarily directly related to the specific growth conditions, it is vital that such films are characterized in a manner that the properties are not dominated by such extrinsic random defects but rather reflect the intrinsic properties of the varied deposition parameters. This approach can be of interest for optimizing growth conditions and analysing magnetic properties of other soft-magnetic films than permalloy as well.

In this study, we prepared sets of thin Py films exhibiting in-plane magnetization with varied deposition methods and parameters and investigated them by analysis techniques that probe the films both globally and locally. In addition, we employ lithographic patterning in order to isolate and distinguish the impact of individual sparsely distributed defects. In this manner, we develop an approach to robustly determine the film properties, so that we can reliably extract the influence of the growth procedure, independent of the presence of random macroscopic defects in the films that can otherwise dominate the properties. We then employ this approach to investigate various methods to reduce the coercivity and effectively control the anisotropy of the deposited films, in particular via the application of rotating magnetic fields during the growth. This approach can be of interest for optimizing growth conditions and analysing magnetic properties of various thin in-plane magnetic films.

II. METHODS

Several sets of samples were produced by room-temperature DC magnetron sputtering in a Singulus Rotaris sputtering system using 10 cm diameter material targets provided by Singulus on 1×1 cm² thermally oxidized (001) p-Si substrates with a 100 nm oxide layer placed close to the rotational axis of the round 8-inch diameter sample holder. Single deposition parameters were systematically varied while keeping the other ones fixed (deposition power in the range 200-1200 W, chamber pressure in the range $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ - $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, or different applied magnetic field protocols).

In order to increase the AMR, which is important for sensing applications, a Ni₄₇Cr₄₂Fe₁₁ seed layer was used, which also drastically improves the (111) texture of the films [48]. The complete material stack included a 4 nm Ni₄₇Cr₄₂Fe₁₁ seed layer, on top of which 30 nm of Py (Ni₈₁Fe₁₉) were deposited; sufficient to provide a measurable change of the magnetic parameters for the different samples and to minimize the impact of interfacial effects such as intermixing that may dominate the properties of thinner films. Finally, a 4 nm Ta capping layer was deposited to prevent oxidation. Ni₄₇Cr₄₂Fe₁₁ and Ta layers were in all cases deposited at the same conditions (800 W and $P_{Ar} = (3.6 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar for the Ni₄₇Cr₄₂Fe₁₁ seed layer and 200 W and $P_{Ar} = (3.5 \pm 0.2) \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar for the Ta capping), with all layer thicknesses controlled by X-ray reflectometry (XRR).

Two different field protocols were investigated, either a so-called “aligning” magnetic field (AMF) that is fixed in space with respect to the rotating sample coordinate frame, or a “rotating” magnetic field (RMF) that is fixed in the laboratory frame and therefore rotates with respect to the film’s frame of reference. While sputtering the Py and Ni₄₇Cr₄₂Fe₁₁ films, rotating or aligning magnetic fields up to 5 mT are generated by 4 pairs of sinusoidally commutated solenoids placed in vacuum around the sample holder. A third set of samples was prepared without applying an additional magnetic field (ZMF).

The deposition tilt was 14° with respect to the substrate normal and the target to substrate distance was 20 cm (Figure 1). During deposition the sample stage was rotated around its axis at a frequency of 1 Hz to provide uniformly thick films, to remove the influence of static background magnetic fields such as the Earth’s and the stray field of the cathode magnets, as well as to avoid self-shadowing [49].

Another set of samples was deposited by thermal evaporation in an ultra-high vacuum

FIG. 1. Schematic illustration of the deposition geometry in the Singulus Rotaris sputtering chamber used to depositing the permalloy thin films.

molecular beam epitaxy chamber on the same substrates, cooled down to liquid nitrogen temperature (no seed layer, 52 nm of Py capped with 4 nm of gold) or at room temperature (25 nm of permalloy capped with 4 nm of gold). Here, the Py evaporator was tilted by 5° with respect to the substrate normal.

The magnetic properties of the prepared samples were investigated both by full-field magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE) microscopy utilizing polarized LED light (field of view $340 \times 450 \mu\text{m}^2$) and vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM). For investigating the anisotropy, magnetic hysteresis loops were recorded for different in-plane rotation angles of the sample with respect to the external magnetic field direction using a 5° to 15° step size. To determine the directions of easy and hard axes the remanent magnetization vs. angle plot was fitted with the function $a \cdot |\cos(\alpha + x)| + c$, where a is a normalization coefficient, α is the rotation angle with respect to the external probing magnetic field and x is the easy axis direction. The anisotropy constant was calculated as the difference between $M_s H_s - \frac{\int_0^{H_s} M_{asc} dH + \int_0^{-H_s} M_{desc} dH}{2}$ for easy and hard axis hysteresis loops [50], where M_s is the saturation magnetization, $M_{asc}(H)$ and $M_{desc}(H)$ are the ascending and descending hysteresis loop branches and H_s is the magnetic field value at which the sample reaches magnetic saturation.

The roughness and average particle size of the samples were measured by atomic force microscopy (AFM), XRR and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The average crystallite size was

obtained using the Scherrer formula to describe the broadening of the Py $\langle 111 \rangle$ XRD peak.

Subsequent patterning of the films into a hexagonal lattice (5×5 mm) of discs with 80 μm diameter and 10 μm spacing was performed using near-ultraviolet photolithography and ma-P 1215 positive photoresist which requires 30" softbaking at 90° C, followed by Ar ion beam etching at 300 V.

III. RESULTS

A first set of Py films was sputtered at room temperature with different adatom energies by varying the sputtering power and chamber pressure, using an external in-plane rotating magnetic field (RMF) of 5 mT. For samples with varied sputtering power the chamber pressure was fixed at $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar and for samples with varied chamber pressure the sputtering power was fixed at 1200 W.

The sputtering rate has a very prominent linear dependence on deposition power and is only slightly affected by the chamber pressure within the investigated region (FIG. 1a). The Scherrer crystallite size is found to vary significantly, and it does not simply follow the adatom energy: the crystallite size increases on lowering the deposition power, which is associated with lowering adatom energies; but it also increases on lowering the Ar pressure, which is associated with higher adatom energies. An AFM image of the sample that is marked with an orange circle in FIG. 1a is shown in the inset. AFM data on average grain size demonstrate a similar trend to the Scherrer crystallite size obtained with XRD. The root-mean-square roughness of all samples, obtained from 5×5 μm^2 AFM scans, is around 0.5 nm and similar for all investigated films.

The magnetic properties of the resulting continuous films, obtained locally using MOKE microscopy and integrating over the whole field of view, are given in FIG. 1b vs. the average crystallite size obtained from XRD. Both, the anisotropy and coercivity of the Py films decrease simultaneously with increasing adatom energy, upon either increasing the sputtering power or lowering the chamber pressure. The thin-film resistivity, in contrast, demonstrates a linear correlation with the Scherrer crystallite size (given in the inset). AMR values defined as: $\Delta R/R = 100 \cdot \frac{R_{\parallel} - R_{\perp}}{R_{\perp}}$ are 2.5 ± 0.2 % for all measured samples. The combined effect of low inert gas pressure and high deposition power resulting in high deposition rates enable

FIG. 2. (a) Sputtering rates (blue dots) and Scherrer average crystallite sizes (red dots) and AFM average grain size (green dots) of Py films sputtered with different powers and chamber pressures. For varied sputtering power the chamber pressure was fixed at $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar and for varied chamber pressure the sputtering power was fixed at 1200 W. Inset: AFM image of the sample marked with an orange circle. (b) Coercivity (blue dots), anisotropy (red dots), and resistivity (green dots) of the continuous permalloy films as a function of the Scherrer average crystallite size for growth with a rotating magnetic field (i.e., fixed in the lab frame) of 5 mT.

achieving low coercivity and anisotropy values down to 0.01 mT and 18 J/m^3 correspondingly of the 30 nm thick Py films sputtered in a RMF while keeping a high AMR ratio.

All samples demonstrate a small but finite anisotropy constant despite the expected disorienting effect of sputtering on the rotating substrate and in RMF to eliminate anisotropy. Rotating magnetic fields in combination with normal incidence of material flow have been reported [32] to produce magnetically isotropic Py films. This discrepancy might be caused by utilizing the $\text{Ni}_{47}\text{Cr}_{42}\text{Fe}_{11}$ seed layer, a tilted sputtering target orientation or a different method/spatial resolution for determining the magnetic properties compared to the referred paper.

Sets of Py film samples sputtered in the absence of magnetic field (zero magnetic field, ZMF), in suppressing magnetic field (rotating magnetic field, RMF) or in aligning magnetic field (static magnetic field, AMF) were investigated by means of both local MOKE microscopy and integral VSM averaging over the whole sample. Local Kerr measurements demonstrate a finite anisotropy for ZMF and RMF with random values and orientations when measured in different spots of the samples. FIG. 2a presents remanence magneti-

sation loops obtained for the ZMF sample (the sample was sputtered at 1200 W power, $P_{Ar}=5.5\cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar) in different spots; a similar behaviour is observed in the case of the RMF sample, while the AMF sample exhibits uniform values of anisotropy and coercivity all over the sample (RMF and AMF samples are not shown). The local magnetic parameters measured in different spots of the continuous films vary in both, the direction and value of the anisotropy, while the easy-axis coercivity remains approximately constant.

VSM results underline these differences (FIG. 2b): Hysteresis curves on the AMF sample demonstrate high squareness in the easy direction and a zero-coercivity loop in the hard direction. The RMF sample demonstrates zero averaged out anisotropy and the ZMF sample still demonstrates low but finite anisotropy.

Varying the strength of the external magnetic field applied during sputtering with the other parameters fixed (chamber pressure $5.5\cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, sputtering power 1200 W, substrate rotation 1 Hz) results in collective changing of coercivity and anisotropy, as shown in FIG. 2c. Small magnetic fields of about 1 mT already suffice to obtain the full effect of the RMF or AMF.

The switching of the continuous films is observed to occur via the formation of magnetization ripple (see inset of FIG. 2c; the sample was sputtered at 1200 W power, $P_{Ar}=5.5\cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, and ZMF) which indicates locally varying directions of the easy axis. For samples sputtered in RMF or ZMF the main ripple orientation does not follow the same direction across the sample but has apparently random orientations in different probed points. This magnetic behaviour of continuous films, i.e. the formation of magnetization ripples in the switching patterns of globally isotropic Py films was reported previously [32].

Various types of magnetic film defects can be sources of local anisotropy. To isolate sparsely distributed sources of stronger anisotropy, that could be causing variations of the magnetic properties in RMF and ZMF sputtered Py films, the films were patterned into arrays of discs. Measurements of the angle-resolved coercivity and remanence magnetization on the patterned samples does not exhibit any notable angular $\frac{\pi}{3}$ -periodicity, so we can exclude a significant contribution of the dipolar interaction between discs. The remanent magnetization states and corresponding magnetization hysteresis curves (solid lines) of two samples are presented in FIG. 3 (1200 W power, $P_{Ar}=5.5\cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, AMF and RMF). The corresponding hysteresis curves obtained for continuous films are given as dashed lines.

Compared to the continuous-film results, the patterned AMF samples retain their easy-

FIG. 3. Influence of aligning (AMF), rotating (RMF) or zero magnetic (ZMF) fields applied during film deposition on the magnetic properties of the continuous films. (a) Normalized polar plots of the remanence magnetisation vs. angle of the field applied during measurement for ZMF. Grey squares sketch the size and relative positions of the areas on the continuous permalloy film that have been probed by MOKE microscopy. (b) Hysteresis loops obtained by VSM for AMF, RMF, and ZMF films. Easy axis loops are given in blue and hard axis loops in red. (c) Easy-axis coercivity (blue dots) and anisotropy constant (red dots) vs. applied magnetic field strength for AMF and RMF geometries as measured by MOKE microscopy. Inset: remanent magnetization pattern of the ZMF sputtered Py film; the indicated external magnetic field direction B coincides with the sensitive orientation of magnetic contrast in the MOKE microscope for all measurements.

axis directions, but the easy-axis hysteresis loops become less square and the hard-axis loops exhibit a higher coercivity when patterned into discs. The hysteresis curves of RMF samples show higher coercivities in all in-plane directions and a completely vanishing anisotropy, which indicates that applying an RMF is an effective strategy to further optimize the permalloy properties.

The magnetic states of demagnetized discs of the presented samples are also qualitatively different: AMF permalloy discs tend to form S-states [51] where the magnetization is predominantly aligned with the easy axis while RMF discs form single vortices with circular magnetization distribution (FIG. 4). For demagnetizing, a gradually decreasing alternating magnetic field was applied in the horizontal direction.

FIG. 4. Magnetic hysteresis loops of the patterned permalloy samples deposited in AMF and RMF (solid lines represent local measurements integrated over the given field of view from MOKE microscopy and dashed lines give integral values obtained from the whole pattern with VSM) and the corresponding remanent magnetization configurations illustrating the switching mechanisms.

IV. DISCUSSION

The deposition method, *fcc* crystal lattice and using the NiCrFe underlayer tend to form textured films with columnar structure with grain size in *z*-direction being close to the film thickness [52]. FIG. 1a demonstrates a significant discrepancy between the XRD and the AFM results. The AFM data is only recording the grain size distribution in the *xy*-plane, which explains the systematically smaller values compared to the Scherrer analysis of the XRD results that implies a spherical shape of the Py crystallites, while these in reality are extended along the growth direction. The observed decrease of the electrical resistivity with increasing grain size that is presented in FIG. 1b is the expected behavior [53] and it supports the performed analysis of the crystallite sizes from the Scherrer data given in FIG. 1a. The surface roughness of our samples is very low and similar for all the samples. With

FIG. 5. Characteristic magnetisation configurations of demagnetized permalloy discs from Kerr microscopy images: (a) S-state for AMF samples and (b) symmetric vortex state for RMF samples and corresponding radial distributions of their magnetization.

all above said, FIG. 1b demonstrates a peculiar non-monotonic dependence of the coercivity and anisotropy of the permalloy films on their average crystallite size. The coercivity of thin permalloy films is generally reported to show a monotonous increase with film thickness and crystallite size for thicknesses above 5 nm [54, 55]. This grain coarsening is caused by Ostwald ripening during deposition at high temperatures and accompanied by a substantial increase in surface roughness [55]. Higher sputter power and lower chamber pressure both increase the adatom energy. Higher adatom energies at lower chamber pressure result in smoother and denser films due to the incorporation of excess atoms in the film causing compressive stress [46] and reducing the coercivity. The same qualitative behaviour is also in agreement with the structure zone model [52] for sputtering, as introduced by Thornton [56]. Decreasing the chamber pressure at fixed high sputter power leads to a transition from the so-called Zone 1 into the transition Zone T, which is accompanied by an increase in grain size. No significant changes in density or roughness of the sputtered films were observed

by XRR, but already minor changes of density and roughness can give rise to significant changes of coercivity.

However, while the chamber pressure has almost no effect on the deposition rate (FIG. 1a), the deposition rate changes proportionally to the sputter power. Changing the sputter power has two effects: while the increased adatom energy still favours larger grains by stronger self-annealing, the increased deposition rate leads to a stronger nucleation (magnetron sputtering of metals starts according to the Volmer–Weber mechanism [57]), resulting in smaller grains, which appears to be the dominant mechanism in the studied films.

Another interesting finding is the non-zero anisotropy of the Py films sputtered onto the rotating substrate in ZMF conditions (FIG. 2). This provides additional insight into the counterplay of the aligning abilities of the tilted target and the external magnetic field. Previous studies demonstrated that without substrate rotation an RMF during deposition results in isotropic Py films only for a normal target position, while target tilt results in a uniaxial anisotropy, where the direction and magnitude are defined by the tilt angle [32]. Another study concluded that the deposition in a static external magnetic field using a tilted target with perpendicular (competing) directions results in a target-tilt-defined anisotropy direction [58]. In our experiment, the aligning effect of the magnetic field prevails the disorientation caused by the target tilt, resulting in a well-defined uniaxial anisotropy (FIG. 2a, AMF sample). Globally isotropic films are only produced by the joint disorienting effect of rotating molecular beam and magnetic field (FIG. 2a, RMF sample).

The microscopic study of the magnetic properties of the samples sputtered in RMF or ZMF demonstrates that within a single field of view significantly varying anisotropy directions and magnitudes coexist. The varying anisotropy directions and magnitudes demonstrated in FIG. 2a cannot be explained by a simple permalloy texture or strain that is uniform across the sample, nor can it be explained by an influence from the edges of the film which would result in a symmetric distribution. One of the possible explanations are random irregularities of the substrate during growth (dust particles, scratches or randomly formed magnetization clusters or voids) orienting the soft Py in an extended region around. Since Py is a very soft magnetic material, such defects can also serve as DW nucleation sites [55] dominating the switching properties of the film and leading to spatially varying properties. In this case, the integral measurements are not necessarily representative of the intrinsic properties of the Py but rather simply probe such random imperfections.

Samples grown by thermal evaporation provide an additional insight into the formation of areas of random anisotropy in Py films. For comparison, we deposited two Py films by thermal evaporation without sample or field rotation in a different UHV deposition chamber, where the sample temperature could be varied. The anisotropy of the Py film deposited on a substrate that was cooled down to liquid-nitrogen temperatures is uniform across the sample and is governed by the tilt of the Py source with respect to the substrate plane. The sample deposited at room temperature with the same source position shows random anisotropy directions and values in different probed areas. Thermal activation during growth at room temperature is already enough to overcome the source-tilt effect and self-anneal the Py film around random defects [59].

In order to isolate single sparsely distributed defects affecting permalloy properties over extended range and to remove the dominance of the defect contributions on the measurement results, the continuous-film samples were patterned into arrays of discs. The disc radii were chosen smaller than the area of uniform ripple orientation but much larger than the permalloy exchange length, the spacing is large enough to avoid interacting with neighbouring discs. Square packaging might be a source of biaxial anisotropy due to the interaction between neighbouring discs, so we have chosen hexagonal arrangement, which also improves the signal to noise ratio of MOKE measurements. In the case of patterned films, the magnetization reversal is governed by the more homogeneous local material parameters as well as by the reduction of stray field energy orienting the magnetic moments along the edges of the discs.

The shape of the hysteresis loops observed for the patterned AMF samples along the easy axis direction is typical for disc-patterned samples [60] and caused by the formation of two magnetization vortices followed by their migration to the disc edge and finally annihilation. Switching along the hard axis occurs through the formation of elongated parallel domains confined by the disc size and results in an increased coercivity of the hysteresis loops. Switching in the RMF samples also takes place through the formation of multidomain states, however they are more complex and show more variation (FIG. 3). The magnetic state of the horizontally demagnetized discs of RMF Py is a symmetric vortex that is the ground state in the discs in the absence of anisotropy. In contrast, the magnetization of the AMF discs reflects the interplay between the introduced anisotropy and the reduction of stray field energy at the edge of the discs, resulting in S-states. Employing this approach to the study of samples exposed to AMFs or RMFs during deposition provides two obser-

vations. First, the AMF results in Py films with uniform magnetic properties and a defined anisotropy direction, despite the disorienting effects of the target tilt caused by substrate rotation. Secondly, patterning of the RMF samples isolates major defects, suppresses the magnetization ripple formation and on the smaller scale, the permalloy films demonstrate isotropic magnetic properties.

In conclusion, we have investigated the effect of varied magnetron sputtering conditions on the magnetic properties of Py, in order to obtain soft-magnetic isotropic thin films. The best samples with lowest coercivity (down to 0.01 mT) and vanishing average anisotropy are obtained using higher sputtering powers (1200 W) and low argon pressures ($4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar). The above discussed approaches were found to improve the magnetic properties of Py by affecting the crystallite size and were reported to lead to the formation of denser and smoother films [46]. They can in turn be combined with the reported AMR enhancement obtained by introducing various seed layers (NiCrFe [48], Pt [61] or CoFeB [62]) to improve the performance of various AMR-based devices performance. We observe a local variation of the magnetic properties of continuous Py films despite using the disorienting effects of sample rotation with respect to the target tilt and the rotating external magnetic field. Patterning of such films into arrays of discs suppresses this variation, which suggests a dominant long-range influence of random defects that affect the magnetic properties of the films in the unpatterned samples. Thus, the investigation of patterned samples provides a general and robust approach to investigate the intrinsic film properties, which can then be unambiguously related to variations in deposition conditions.

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